

Original Article

Visibility and research impact of Bulgarian geographers: insights from indexing databases and social media platforms

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Declaration of Interests

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Abstract

Background: The requirement of publishing high-quality papers in established peer-reviewed journals is still in the early days of implementation among academic geographers in Bulgaria, which limits the visibility and impact of Bulgarian research and delays the possibilities of academic recognition and international collaboration.

Objectives: To examine the current visibility and impact of Bulgarian geographers using quantitative analysis of publicly available data derived from eight scientometric databases and social media platforms.

Methods: Relevant data were collected for 116 researchers affiliated with five institutions from the following sources: Scopus, Web of Science, Publons, ORCID, Google Scholar, Research Gate, LinkedIn, and X (Twitter). Using Microsoft Excel, the performance of each of the researchers and each of the institutions was quantified in terms of (1) the number of publications, (2) the number of citations, (3) H-index, (4) i10-index, and (5) Research Interest Score. The scores were also plotted using RAWGraphs and Microsoft PowerPoint.

Results: Only half of the researchers had published in internationally indexed journals. The institutions and departments in the capital city, Sofia, enjoyed significantly and disproportionately higher visibility than those from smaller towns. Geographers from the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Sofia) and one department from Sofia University showed the highest visibility on Scopus (100%), whereas two rural universities – the University of Veliko Tarnovo and Shumen University – were visible mostly on ResearchGate and Google Scholar. Overall visibility of each institution on social media was very low (8%–16%).

Conclusions: The analysis led to several recommendations on increasing the visibility and impact of Bulgarian research in geography. These recommendations will be valuable in research management, public relations, especially in improving communications and devising development strategies.

Keywords: Google Scholar, ResearchGate, science communication, scientometrics, Scopus

Introduction

Academic careers and research publications go hand in hand, each complementing the other. As the publishing industry – especially scholarly publishing – continues to improve its quality and standards, these improvements in the form of innovations and trends affect the career development of academics. Research institutions use global sources of scientometric information such as Scopus and the Web of Science (WoS) to benchmark individual researchers and research units and to decide on career progression for their staff. This process is usually framed by national legislation and closely monitored by specific agencies.

In recent years, scholarly publishing in Bulgaria has been transformed, stimulated by legislation on the development of academic staff.¹ With this legislation, Bulgaria has tried to improve the mechanism for the career development of scientific staff and to align it with the highest international standards. The main change was that, for the first time, researchers were required to have published a specified number of papers in international peer-reviewed journals that are indexed by the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. This meant that all researchers aspiring to move from junior positions to senior positions must (1) publish a specified number of papers; (2) attract a specified number of citations for those papers; and (3) attain a specified value of the H-index. Issues with research policy and scientometrics as understood in Bulgaria were addressed almost 10 years ago^{2,3} and further developed through a survey of university academics to reveal the effectiveness of traditional scientometrics in tackling fake science.⁴ To date, all academic development procedures in Bulgaria are monitored by the Ministry of Education and Science through the National

Centre for Information and Documentation (NACID).⁵ In particular, NACID collects information on academic staff at all levels of career development from the level of an assistant to that of a full professor. This information is checked, stored, and published in special registers and databases, which are then used to inform various procedures related to doctoral defence and recruitment.

It is now almost 15 years since the adoption of the new rules for career development in Bulgarian science¹ and the attempts to impose a 'smarter' geography and incentivize publication activity.^{6–8} However, no analysis of the relevant scientometric data to assess how academic geographers have responded to the new standards has so far been undertaken. This is a significant gap in knowledge because delays in meeting the new standards could negatively affect scientific progress in general. Notably, the law allows the publication of scientific monographs (defined as a publication with at least 100 standard pages) in the assessment criteria for academic advancement to either Associate Professor or Professor. A monograph is judged as equivalent to 10 published articles indexed in Scopus or WoS. Of course, whether one monograph can truly be considered equivalent to 10 peer-reviewed papers in internationally indexed journals is debatable. Moreover, Geography is the only discipline among the Earth Sciences in Bulgaria (including Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Mathematics, and Informatics) in which different quartiles of Scopus and WoS indexed journals are not taken into account in the assessment for career advancement. In other words, every published journal article brings in 100 points regardless of whether it is published in a journal in the first quartile, the fourth quartile, or anything in between. This has led to the risk of accumulating publications in low-quality

conference proceedings or journals with dubious peer-review processes – a situation that has been seen as a major driver of the emergence and proliferation of fraudulent science and promotion of poorly qualified candidates as professors in Bulgarian sciences.²

In our experience with Bulgarian procedures in the field of geoscience, most geographers prefer to publish monographs rather than multiple papers as a means of career advancement, a preference that could affect the overall quality of scientific output in general. At the same time, Bulgarian scientists who receive funding for their training are expected to publish in internationally indexed journals, preferably open access. And yet, in our experience, a significant number of Bulgarian researchers in the geographical sciences lack the required knowledge and skills to publish in international journals and to avoid undesirable publishing practices (for example, publishing in predatory journals). These problems put academics under severe pressure to publish, often result in publications in low-quality, fraudulent, or even predatory journals,⁹ leading to valuable findings being lost as they remain unread and uncited, by the international geographic research community.

A closer look at publicly available data on published research output of Bulgarian geographers could provide a more detailed picture of how universities and research institutes can improve their publication record.¹⁰ Analyzing these data can show if there are differences between institutions based in the capital city, Sofia, and those based in more rural, small-town areas, and between universities and individual research institutes. Such analysis can be further used for self-improvement by individual researchers and for better planning of institutional development and publishing activities and strategies.^{11,12}

The aim of this study was therefore to investigate the ‘visibility’, and hence the impact, of Bulgarian researchers in geography and geographical sciences by analysing the coverage of their output in global indexing databases and social media platforms. To achieve this goal, we undertook two major research tasks:

- collect data from eight databases and platforms that publish scientometric data and
- analyze the visibility and influence of Bulgarian geographers at the institutional level and at the level of the individual author in terms of the number of papers published, the number of citations, and H-index.

Methods

The study was performed in three steps (Figure 1), which are described in detail in the following subsections: Step one was the preparation and started with the selection of the leading geographic institutions and data acquisition; Step two comprized data processing and calculations of general metrics revealing the overall institutional and author’s impact; and Step three comprized data analysis and visualization to generate results and draw conclusions on the visibility and impact of Bulgarian geographers.

Step one: data acquisition

Data were obtained from publicly available sources including institutional websites, databases, and social platforms. First, we identified the primary institutions in Bulgaria with Geography departments (Table 1).

Next, we obtained the relevant information about the current research staff from the official websites of the departments and faculties of the five selected institutions.

To analyze the visibility and impact of each researcher, we selected eight of the most frequently and globally used indexing databases

Figure 1. Workflow of the study

and social media platforms: Scopus, Web of Science, ex-Publons (by the Reviewers tab on the WoS Researcher ID profile), ORCID, Google Scholar, Research Gate, LinkedIn, and X (Twitter). For all platforms, information about the visibility of a particular geographer was obtained manually by identifying whether they had a profile on that platform. Information regarding their impact was also collected manually by recording the following metrics from their profile: number of documents (Scopus, WoS, Google Scholar, ResearchGate), number of citations (Scopus, WoS, Google Scholar, ResearchGate), H-index (Scopus, WoS, Google Scholar, ResearchGate), i10-index (Google Scholar), and Research Interest Score (ResearchGate). These data were obtained over two periods, namely 28–29 July 2022 and 20–21 December 2023. The list of people was updated to reflect those who had retired or joined in the meantime. Further updates and post-processing of the

collected data were carried out in late January 2024. Final information about the number of documents, citations, and H-index of all geographers along with their IDs and links was updated between 31 January 2024 and 2 February 2024. This was the version used for data processing and analysis.

Step two: data processing

The collected data are listed in Supplementary Material 1 (as MS Excel spreadsheets) arranged by the institution, department, and faculty. Personal data, including the name in Bulgarian and English and profile IDs, were removed and replaced with a simple numeral (serial numbers from 1 to 116) as an identifier. The data include professional position, level of education (title), primary affiliation (institution, faculty, and department), and the presence or absence in each of the eight databases and social platforms, where ‘0’ indicates no

Table 1. Distribution of Bulgarian researchers among five primary academic institutions in geography and their subdivisions. The institution numbers correspond to those shown on the map in Figure 1 (top panel; Step 1).

No.	Faculty	Department	No. of researchers (n = 116) n (%)
1	Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Sofia (SU) Faculty of Geology and Geography	Geography of Tourism;	12
		Regional Development;	10
		Climatology, Hydrology and Geomorphology;	9
		Social and Economic Geography;	8
		Regional and Political Geography;	8
		Geospatial Systems and Technologies;	9
		Landscape Ecology and Environmental Protection	6
			62 (53%)
2	National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia (NIGGG-BAS) Department of Geography	Geographic Information Systems;	8
		Economic and Social Geography;	7
		Physical Geography;	4
		19 (16%)	
3	South-West University Neofit Rilski, Blagoevgrad (SWU) Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences	Geography, Ecology and Environmental Protection	13 (11%)
4	St. Cyril and St. Methodius University of Veliko Tarnovo, Veliko Tarnovo (UVT) Faculty of History	Geography	14 (12%)
5	Shumen University Bishop Konstantin Preslavski, Shumen (ShU) Faculty of Natural Sciences	Geography, Regional Development and Tourism	8 (7%)*

*The total is 99% because percentages were rounded.

profile and '1' indicates that the researcher had a profile. Where multiple affiliations existed, only the primary affiliation was recorded.

We then calculated the total numbers and relative frequencies of people in an institution who had profiles on all eight databases and platforms. After that, the minimum and maximum values of all metrics were obtained to present the overall range between institutions. Average values of H-index, citations, number of publications, i10-index, and Research Interest Score were then calculated.

Step three: data analysis and visualization

To obtain an overview of the visibility of each department on a particular database or platform, we produced a matrix plot in

RAWGraphs¹³ organized along two axes: the 13 geographical departments at the lowest level of organization plus one category for all researchers across all institutes along the Y axis and the eight databases and platforms along the X axis. Values at the intersection represent the total percentage of appearances of geographers in a given department.

To present the overall visibility of Bulgarian geographers and to compare them by primary institutions, we used a simple percentage bar chart generated in MS Excel (Figure 3) and refined in MS PowerPoint. Eight charts were generated, one for each of the eight indexing databases or social platforms on which aggregated information about the visibility of geographers is represented for the five primary institutions.

The number of documents, the number of citations, and H-index of Bulgarian geographers at an institutional level are compared using box-and-whisker plots (Figure 4): Figure 4a for the number of documents; Figure 4b for the number of citations, and Figure 4c for the H-index. Each group contains six plots, five for the primary geographic institutions and one for all institutions. Each of the four databases and platforms used for calculating the metrics are shown: Scopus, WoS, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate.

Additional data on author metrics from Google Scholar (i10-index) and ResearchGate (Research Interest Score) are represented in Figure 5. Finally, the institutions were compared on the overall institutional performance.

Ethics

This study did not involve human participants. All data was anonymised.

Results

Visibility at the department level

The overall visibility of Bulgarian geographers in the selected databases and platforms was 54%, meaning that more than half of the 116 researchers had their profiles on the selected databases and platforms. ResearchGate appears to be the most frequently used social platform for communicating the results of research (83% of the researchers had a profile), whereas X (Twitter), at 10%, was the least used platform (Figure 2a, last row).

The matrix plot (Figure 2a) shows a solid cluster of five relatively high-performing departments with several instances of all the staff researchers having profiles in one or more of the databases and platforms. The

five departments comprised three geographical sections of the National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia (NIGGG-BAS), one department of the Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Sofia (SU), and the Geography department of the South-West University Neofit Rilski, Blagoevgrad (SWU).

A closer look showed that only two departments had the distinction of having all their staff represented in four or more of the selected databases and platforms. The Department of Landscape Ecology and Environmental Protection (LEEP) at SU was the most visible, scoring 88% on visibility; in other words, all its staff had a presence in six out of the eight platforms (ORCID, Google Scholar, Research Gate, LinkedIn, Scopus, and WoS). The second most visible, at 80%, was the Section of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) at the NIGGG-BAS: all its staff were represented in four out of the eight platforms (ORCID, Research Gate, Scopus, and WoS).

At the lower end in terms of visibility – below 40% – were a cluster of departments from SU (39%) and the Geography departments of both geographical departments of Shumen University Bishop Konstantin Preslavski, Shumen (ShU; 35%) and the St. Cyril and St. Methodius University of Veliko Tarnovo, Veliko Tarnovo (UVT; 33%).

The visibility of the remaining seven departments varied between 49% for the Department of Geography of Tourism at SU and 69% for the Department of Physical Geography at NIGGG-BAS.

Only two departments had all their staff represented on both the major databases, namely Scopus and WoS. These departments were the Landscape Ecology and Environmental

Figure 2. Percentage of Bulgarian geographers with accounts on one or more of eight indexing databases and social media platforms.

(Legend: A: Percentage of researchers by their department. G, Geography (UVT); GRDT, Geography, Regional Development and Tourism (ShU); GT, Geography of Tourism (SU); RD, Regional Development (SU); CHG, Climatology, Hydrology and Geomorphology (SU); SEG, Social and Economic Geography (SU); RPG, Regional and Political Geography (SU); GST, Geospatial Systems and Technologies (SU); LEEP, Landscape Ecology and Environmental Protection (SU); GIS, Geographic Information Systems (NIGGG-BAS); ESG, Economic and Social Geography (NIGGG-BAS); PG, Physical Geography (NIGGG-BAS); GEEP, Geography, Ecology and Environmental Protection (SWU). B: Percentage of researchers, by institution. UVT, St. Cyril and St. Methodius University of Veliko Tarnovo; ShU, Shumen University Bishop Konstantin Preslavski; SU, Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski; SWU, South-West University Neofit Rilski; NIGGG-BAS, National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences.)

Protection (LEEP) of SU and the GIS Section of NIGGG-BAS.

Visibility at institutional level

ResearchGate, ORCID, Scopus, and WoS were the most popular among Bulgarian

geographers (Figures 2b and 3). Of these, ResearchGate appears to be the most popular: two institutions (NIGGG-BAS and SWU) had 100% visibility; another two (ShU and SU), 80%–90% visibility; and one (UVT), almost 60%.

Figure 3. Presence of Bulgarian geographers in each of the eight databases, by institution (Legend: NIGGG-BAS – National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences; SWU – South-West University; ShU – Shumen University; SU – Sofia University; UVT – University of Veliko Tarnovo).

Figure 4. Publication metrics from four scientometric databases, namely Scopus (orange), Web of Science (WoS; purple), Google Scholar (light blue), and ResearchGate (green).

(Legend: A: total number of articles; B: total number of citations; C: H-index. UVT – University of Veliko Tarnovo; SU – Sofia University; NIGGG-BAS – National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences; ShU – Shumen University; SWU – South-West University; Total: all institutions.)

Figure 5. Publication metrics from Google Scholar and ResearchGate.

(Legend: A: i10-index (from Google Scholar); B: detailed view of the panel marked in A; C: Research Interest Score (from ResearchGate); D: detailed view of the panel marked in C; Total, all institutions. UVT – University of Veliko Tarnovo; SU – Sofia University; NIGGG-BAS – National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences; ShU – Shumen University; SWU – South-West University.)

Most (92%) of the researchers at NIGGG-BAS have an ORCID profile.

Almost 90% of the researchers from SWU, followed by those from NIGGG-BAS, appeared to use the reviewer services and sought editorial recognition on the Peer Review tab of their WoS user profiles (ex-Publons).

Only one institution (NIGGG-BAS) had full visibility (100%) on Scopus: all its researchers had their individual profiles in that database. It was also the most visible (a score of almost 90%) among the five institutions on WoS.

X (Twitter) was the least used social media platform at an institutional level (on average, fewer than 20% of the researchers from a given institution had a profile). Only a few researchers from NIGGG-BAS, SU, and

SWU – and none from UVT and ShU – had a profile on X.

Authors' impact at institutional level: key metrics

Number of articles

The number of published articles per researcher varied from 35 to 200, as seen on their respective profiles on Scopus, WoS, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate (Figure 4a).

The total number of documents attributed to Bulgarian geographers across the four databases was 5254, although only 997 of them were indexed in both Scopus and WoS. The highest number of documents, as calculated for all five institutions taken together on different databases, was 2445 on ResearchGate, 1812 on Google Scholar, 610 on Scopus, and 387 on WoS.

Number of citations

The minimum number of citations per researcher for Google Scholar was 1, whereas the maximum was almost 5000 (Figure 4b). The corresponding numbers for Scopus were 1 and 3106.

The total number of citations for all Bulgarian geographers across all databases was 32,179, distributed as follows: ResearchGate, 10,882; Google Scholar, 10,578; Scopus, 6477; and WoS, 4272.

H-index

H-index is a measure of how many papers are cited how many times: for instance, an H-index of 5 means that 5 papers were cited at least 5 times each. Statistics for the H-index are presented in Figure 4c. The highest value of H-indices as calculated across all five institutions was for Research Gate (334), followed by Google Scholar (253), Scopus (201), and WoS (116). NIGGG-BAS had the highest overall H-index, whereas the UVT had the lowest.

i10-index

The i10-index is specific to Google Scholar and shows the number of papers, each of which has been cited at least 10 times: for instance, an i10-index of 7 means that seven papers have been cited at least 10 times. Statistics for the i10-index are presented in Figures 5, a and b. NIGGG-BAS had the highest median value of 1, whereas UVT recorded the lowest value of 0. NIGGG-BAS also had the highest value of 32, whereas ShU and SWU each had the lowest value of 1.75. The i10-index for the majority of researchers at UVT was between 1 and 4, and 3 out of 19 had values between 12 and 32. In SU, 8 researchers had the highest values ranging from 3 to 18, whereas in ShU and SWU, only one researcher showed the highest value of 1.

Research Interest Score

Research Interest Score is specific to ResearchGate and represents a combination of the number of reads by unique ResearchGate members, the number of recommendations on ResearchGate, and citations (excluding self-citations). The median Research Interest Score was the highest for SU, at about 120, followed by NIGGG-BAS, at about 110 (Figures 5, c and d). Two geographers from NIGGG-BAS recorded the highest values of more than 3500 and 1000, whereas the lowest value, at about 230, was for one researcher from ShU.

Discussion

Although the presence of Bulgarian geographers in academic databases and social platforms and the impact of their work (in terms of bibliometrics) have been discussed earlier, to the authors' knowledge, they have never been quantified before. The present study shows significant differences in visibility and metrics between geographical institutions based in Sofia (the capital city) and those based in more rural or small-town universities. Institutions with a longer history of geographic research,^{14,8} for instance SU and NIGGG-BAS, had a higher overall visibility and impact, probably because of their greater staff strength (81 out of the total sample of 116 researchers) and longer tradition of international collaboration, the researchers themselves being the main drivers who create opportunities for quality research, publications, and funding.

The analysis also identified several departments showing higher values of the metrics of impact. These departments undertake research in relatively new scientific fields and use more advanced techniques in

landscape ecology, environmental protection, GIS, and remote sensing. Recent reviews focusing on the development of specific fields, such as geography of tourism¹⁵ and ecosystem services,¹⁶ could be used as a background to obtain a more detailed view of the contemporary development of geography in Bulgaria. Such research could identify the 'hot topics' in geography and provide valuable evidence for better planning and strategic development at the institutional level as well as at the individual level. Surveys of lecturers and students from a range of scientific fields⁴ are too broad to provide information relevant to geographers but serve as good examples of collecting empirical data on the research question in this study. Therefore, such surveys need better methodologies.

Our results showed geographers from the NIGGG-BAS, SWU, and SU to be more productive and more visible on the WoS and Scopus, whereas those from ShU and the UVT were more visible on ResearchGate and Google Scholar. More research is needed to see if this lack of visibility of ShU and UVT in the WoS and Scopus is related to, or due to, ignorance of good publishing practices, failure to realize the limitations of publishing in grey literature, or limited skills in communicating their science in languages other than a researcher's native language.

Even if it has been suggested that using social media enhances the impact of published papers¹⁷ and communication attitudes,¹⁸ Bulgarian geographers are yet to learn to take full advantage of social media. Fewer than 16% of the geographers in three out of five institutions – and none from the ShU and the UVT – have accounts on X or LinkedIn. The overall lack of appreciation of the power of social media for academia might be considered one of the key factors

for the lower visibility on specific academic platforms and databases. For instance, if authors do not share their newly published paper with their professional contacts, it is less likely that someone will find it and read it. Enough guidance is available on how academics should use social media, a particularly good example being 'The role of social media in journal publishing',¹⁹ which provides a process model of five research activities – networking, framing, investigating, disseminating, and assessing – that social media could be used for.²⁰

Besides further research on the publication performance of Bulgarian geographers, additional actions in education, training, and knowledge-raising are needed. Recent studies make recommendations to different stakeholders in academia on how to improve visibility and citation impact. For instance, authors should be aware of the publishing and indexing mechanisms and take advantage of them to make their high-quality papers as impactful as possible.²¹ Similar issues have been identified in other scientific fields such as medicine,²² and studies reporting those issues also provide some ideas on how journal editors can help authors write strong papers. Better writing skills are indeed a key element in advancing scientific careers because good writing can lead to higher values of several scientometric measures. Such education, training, and knowledge-raising among Bulgarian geographers should be led by experts in international publishing and indexing. Here, the Bulgarian Geographical Society and its flagship periodical – the *Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society* – arguably have the most experience, being the first internationally indexed title in Geography from Bulgaria. Editors, reviewers, and authors should be more active in communicating high standards and promoting best practices in academic publishing not only among

Bulgarian scholars but also beyond the country's borders.

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